

SOCIAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS CONTRIBUTING TO BEHAVIOR DISORDERS IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

Farmanova Gulbakhor Khushbakovna

Director of Preschool and School Education Department 29 State Preschool
Education Organization, Surkhandarya region Jarkurgon district
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13853880>

Abstract: this article examines social and psychological factors contributing to behavior disorders in preschool children.

Key words: socio-psychological factors, family education, social environment, behavioral disorder, emotional distress

The problem of children's behavior in a social environment is a relevant topic today. This is especially true for preschool children, who add to the statistics on the increase in children with pronounced signs of behavioral disorders in society. Restless behavior, incontinence, mood swings, difficulties in organizing any activity create many problems for a child in any situation of interaction with peers and adults. Scientific literature describes various causes of behavioral disorders in children, but there is no generally accepted classification of deviant behavior.

In this case, the family plays a major role among the above-mentioned reasons, since it is impossible to explain the child's behavioral disorders outside the context of the analysis of the socio-psychological situations of his development. The family is the object that has been studied in different years by many researchers and is the immediate environment that forms the moral values of the child. Consequently, the family is one of the most important factors in the socialization of the preschooler's personality, and in case of a violation of relations in the "family-personality" system - the emergence of deviance.

A family is a small group based on marriage or blood relationship, the members of which are connected by a common life, mutual moral responsibility and mutual assistance; it develops a set of norms, sanctions and patterns of behavior that regulate the interaction between spouses, parents and children, and children among themselves. The most important characteristic of the family is its functions, which are in a certain correspondence with the nature of social relations. In this regard, scientists predict that the main function of the family may be the function of early socialization, due to the fact that early socialization is most favorable in the family. The family provides a connection between the individual and social, economic and demographic processes in society. The family as a social institution has changed significantly at present. It experiences

significant difficulties in adapting to the dynamic development of modern society.

The family is extremely sensitive to all processes that occur in society, it responds to them in one way or another. The difficulties and contradictions of the historical development of our society have left their mark on the life of the family and its educational opportunities. Socio-psychological causes of deviant behavior in preschool children. Family dysfunction can be attributed to the socio-psychological causes of deviant behavior in childhood. Family dysfunction is one of the main reasons determining the state and dynamics of deviant behavior in minors.

The concept of “family dysfunction” covers various negative characteristics of the family, defects in its structural, quantitative or age-sex composition, intra-family relationships, relationships of family members with external social institutions – kindergarten, school, college, production, leisure and other institutions. Two areas of risk of socio-psychological factors can be distinguished that contribute to the development of behavioral disorders in children:

The family is a key condition for the optimal psycho-social development of a child and most often acts as a source of age-related psycho-emotional development disorders. Usually, when a problematic situation arises that is unacceptable for a child, creating certain difficulties for him and leading to experiences, resentments, and hurt pride, it acts as a stimulus, plays the role of a trigger. When the stimulus reaches a critical threshold, it causes a response, with the help of which the child tries to relieve, throw off the experiences that are burdensome for him. Childhood distress in the emotional sphere manifests itself

in aggression, uncontrollability or anxiety, insecurity, isolation or a tendency to fear. It is very important that the emotional state of the child is favorable, since the accumulation of negative emotions also affects the somatic health of the child.

In addition to social family factors, teachers and other adults who are around the student throughout the day can be the cause of problems in the emotional-behavioral sphere and cognitive activity. The fact is that children are often influenced not only by deliberate and targeted actions of an educational nature, but also by the behavioral characteristics of adults who are nearby throughout the day. In order for the incorrect behavior of adults in an educational institution not to be a source of aggressive behavior of a child, it is necessary to follow certain rules and the Code of Pedagogical Ethics. In order to effectively prevent and correct deviant behavior of preschool children, it is necessary to study the complex of reasons that cause deviations in the child's behavior and remember that children are very sensitive and react clearly to the mood of people around them, even if adults do not notice it.

Thus, eliminating the adverse effects of socio-psychological factors or mitigating their impact on the child's development will contribute to a more correct and harmonious development, and will also reduce the risk of impaired personality development and the neuropsychic sphere.

References:

1. Batirov M. (2023). Causes of deviant behavior in preschool children. Bulletin of Nizhnevartovsk State University, (3), 124-131.
2. Komilova N. (2022). Development of emotional responsiveness as a condition for preventing deviant behavior in preschool children. Siberian Psychological Journal, (36), 68-71.
3. Development of social emotions in preschool children: Psychological research / Ed. A.V. Zaporozhets, Ya.Z. Neverovich. Edition-3. M.: Pedagogy, 2023

